

Extraction of Rhenium (VII) with Rhodamine B Hydrochloride

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The extraction of Re(VII) with RH^+Cl^- into organic solvents has been investigated. Nitrobenzene, which is the most efficient extractant for Re(VII), is used to separate Re(VII) from other elements. The mechanism of the extraction of Re(VII) into nitrobenzene has been elucidated.

Metals forming singly charged chloroanions are extracted with rhodamine B(R) into organic solvents from hydrochloric acid solution. A number of investigators have studied the extraction of Sb(V)^{1-3} , Ga(III)^4 , Au(III)^5 and Tl(III)^6 with R. However, the extraction of rhenium (VII) with this reagent has not been reported. The present paper describes a detailed study on the extractive behaviour of rhenium (VII) with rhodamine B hydrochloride (RH^+Cl^-).

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals and Apparatus : Reagents grade (99% purity) rhodamine B hydrochloride (RH^+Cl^-) of B.D.H. make was used in extraction studies. All other reagents and solvents were of A.R. grade. The preparation of rhenium solutions and apparatus employed for various measurements are described elsewhere⁷. The carrier solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate salts in double-distilled water. Radioisotopes were supplied by the Isotope Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay.

Extraction Procedure : 1 ml. of potassium perrhenate solution containing 16–1000 μg . of Re (VII) labelled with Re-186 was taken in a 100 ml. separatory funnel. 2 ml. of RH^+Cl^- solution in alcohol were added. The acidity of the mixture was adjusted with HCl or NaOH, keeping the total volume to 20 ml. The mixture was equilibrated for 2 minutes with 20 ml. of nitrobenzene. The two phases were allowed to separate. Each phase was removed and centrifuged. The activity of 1 ml. of each phase was measured on a gamma-ray spectrometer. The pH of the equilibrated aqueous phase was recorded. The extraction of other ions were followed by using radioactive tracers. Beta-emitting radioisotopes were counted on a thin end-window type G.M. counter after evaporating the solution to dryness. All necessary corrections were applied. Total activity could be accounted for within $\pm 2\%$. Extraction studies were also carried out by equilibrating aqueous solution of rhenium (VII) with nitrobenzene solution of RH^+Cl^- .

1. S. H. Webster and J. T. Fairhall, *J. Ind. Hyg. Toxicol.*, 1945, **27**, 184.
2. V. T. Kuznetsov, *Compt. rend., Acad. Sci., U.R.S.S.*, 1946, **52**, 231.
3. R. W. Ramette and E. B. Sandell, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1955, **13**, 159.
4. H. Onishi and E. B. Sandell, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1955, **13**, 159.
5. B. T. Macnulty and L. D. Woolard, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1955, **13**, 154.
6. H. Onishi, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan.*, 1956, **29**, 945.
7. Shankar K. Iyer and B. C. Haldar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1043.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The extraction (Table I) of rhenium(VII) into nitrobenzene from aqueous-alcoholic solution containing RH^+Cl^- is better than 99% over the pH range 0.2–4.5; it decreases to 75% at pH 7.5. In the pH range 0.2–4.5, the extraction equilibrium is reached within 2 minutes and the separation of the two phases is rapid. Extraction data (Table I) indicate that the extraction of rhenium (VII) by organic solvents from aqueous-alcoholic solution of pH 2.8 decreases in the series.

TABLE I

Extraction Coefficients of Rhenium (VII) between an Organic Solvent and an Aqueous-Alcoholic Solution of RH^+Cl^-

Rhenium(VII) taken = 29 μ g
 Volume of organic phase = 20 ml
 Temperature = 31° \pm 1°

Aqueous-alcoholic phase = 20 ml
 of aqueous solution contain-
 ing 2 ml. of 2% solution of
 RH^+Cl^- in alcohol.

Solvent	pH	Extraction Coefficient (E _i)	% Extraction
Nitrobenzene (NB.)	0.2	147	99.33
"	1.2	217	99.63
"	1.9	360	99.73
"	2.5	520	99.83
"	2.8	651	99.88
"	3.0	502	99.80
"	3.7	285	99.63
"	4.5	100	99.03
"	5.6	4.5	81.80
"	7.5	3.0	75.00
Ethyl acetate (EtAc)	2.8	21.0	95.45
Isoamyl alcohol (AMoH)	2.8	14.0	93.33
Octanol (Oc OH)	2.8	10.0	90.9
Amyl acetate (Am Ac)	2.8	4.0	80.0
Chloroform	2.8	4.0	80.0
Methyl isobutyl ketone (MEK)	2.8	1.0	50.0
Benzene (Bz)	2.8	0.66	39.76
Carbon tetrachloride	2.8	0.01	0.99

TABLE II

*Effect of Salts on the Extraction Coefficient of Rhenium(VII)*Aqueous phase = 20 ml. solution containing 40 mg. of RH^+Cl^- in 2 ml. of alcohol and added salts

Organic phase = 20 ml. of nitrobenzene.

 $\text{pH} = 2.8$.Temperature = $31^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Salt added	Conc. in Molarity	Extraction Coefficient of Rhenium(VII) (E)
KCl	0.0726—0.3463	395—171
NH_4Cl	0.0535—0.4280	306—136
MgCl_2	0.1253—0.5112	343—72
KBr	0.0400	66.0
$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$	0.1007	45.0
NaNO_3	0.0500	13.0
HgCl_2	0.0360	1.0
KI	0.1505	0.9

The effect of alcohol concentration on the extraction coefficient (E) of rhenium (VII) was studied by adding 2–10 ml. of alcohol to the aqueous phase. Under identical experimental conditions, the value of E for rhenium(VII) decreases with the increase in the percentage of alcohol added to the aqueous phase. The variation of initial concentration of rhenium (VII) in the aqueous phase from $4.29 \mu\text{M/litre}$ to $296.3 \mu\text{M/litre}$ does not cause appreciable ($< 8\%$) change in the E value for rhenium (VII). However, when the initial concentration of rhenium(VII) is raised to $805.1 \mu\text{M/litre}$, the E value decreases to 205, though the molar ratio of $\text{RH}^+\text{Cl}^- : \text{Re(VII)}$ is 2.07. The extraction coefficient of rhenium(VII) is affected by the presence of chlorides of potassium, ammonium and magnesium, potassium bromide, sodium thiosulfate and sodium nitrite. The extractions of rhenium (VII) from $0.036M \text{HgCl}_2$ and $0.150M \text{KI}$ solution are 50% and 47% respectively.

Extraction studies with various elements show that Ag(I), Tc(VII), Mo(VI), Pd(II), Au(III), Hg(II) and Ru(III) are extracted to the extent of 50% or more. The extraction of Zr(IV), Fe(III) and W(VI) are 6.1%, 0.99% and 0.90% respectively, and those of other elements investigated are less than 0.2%. Sodium sulphide lowers the extraction of Hg(II) to 0.3%. In the presence of fluoride, the extractions of Zr(IV) and Mo(VI) are 0.1% and 6.0% respectively. Sodium sulfite suppresses the extraction of Pd(II) to less than 0.3%. Hydroquinone reduces the extraction of Au(III) to 1%. By masking Ru(III) with EDTA, its extraction can be reduced to 1%. Sodium thiosulfate lowers the extraction of Ag(I) to 0.3%. But $0.1007M$ sodium thiosulfate solution reduces the extraction of rhenium (VII) from 99.8% to 97.8%.

The values of separation factor (S , defined as the ratio of the extraction coefficient of rhenium(VII) to the extraction coefficient of the element of interest) for various elements are given in Table III. These values have been confirmed by separating microgram amounts of rhenium(VII) from 10 mg. of each of the following elements : Ce(III and IV), Zn(IV), Zr(IV), Co(II), Mn(II), Cd(II), Cu(II), Cs(III), As(III), Sb(III), Sn(IV) and Fe(III). The separation was achieved by extracting rhenium (VII) into 20 ml. of nitrobenzene solution of RH^+Cl^- from aqueous solution of pH 2.8 containing appropriate masking agent

TABLE III

Separation Factors for various elements

Organic phase = 20 ml. of nitrobenzene containing 40 mg. of the reagent.

Aqueous phase = 20 ml. of aqueous solution at pH 2.8 containing 3 mg.

of Re(VII) plus element of interest

Temperature = $31^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Separation on factor greater than	Element
10 ⁶	La(III), Zn(II) ^a , Cs(I) ^a , Co(II) ^a , Nd(III), Mn (II), As (III).
10 ⁵	Zn(II), Co(II), Sb(III), Cu(II), Cr(III), Mn(II) ^a , P(V), S(VI), Ir(IV) ^a , Sn(IV), Zr(IV), Fe(III) ^a , Cd(II), Ag(I), ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$) ^b and Pd(II), ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$) ^b , Ce(III).
10 ⁴	W(VI) ^a , Fe(III), Cd(II) ^a , Ru(III), (EDTA) ^b , Hg(II) (Na_2S) ^a ; ^b , Au(III) (Hydroquinone) ^b , Ce(IV).
10 ³	Zn(IV) ^a , Ru(III) ^a , Mo(IV), (NaF) ^a ^b
10 ²	Ru(III), Ag(I) ^a , Pd(II), Mo(VI).
10	Mo(VI) ^a , Au(III) ^a , Pd(II) ^a .

a = Carrier free or less than 1 μg .

b = masking agent added.

(if necessary), followed by washing the organic phase with an equal volume of aqueous solution at pH 8.2 and stripping rhenium(VII) from the organic phase by equilibrating twice with 5 ml. of 10M NaOH solution. The same procedure permitted to separate 25 μg . of Re(VII) from 1 mg. of Mo(VI). The recovery of rhenium(VII) was greater than 98% and other elements in the recovered rhenium were less than one microgram. Total time required for each separation never exceeded 10 mins. 20 ml. of nitrobenzene could extract up to 3 mg. of Re(VII) .

The high extraction coefficient value of rhenium(VII) between nitrobenzene solution of RH^+Cl^- and aqueous solution of pH 2.8 seems to suggest that rhenium(VII) is extracted as ion pairs. Conductivity measurements with nitrobenzene solution of RH^+Cl^- show that it conducts poorly (8.8–12.6 mhos) in the concentration range ($1.043\text{--}4.065 \times 10^{-3}M$) used in the extraction experiments, though the molar conductance (21.9 mhos) of its dilute solution ($3.37 \times 10^{-5}M$) in nitrobenzene approaches to that of I : I type of electrolytes⁸.

8. R. A. Robinson and R. H. Stokes, 'Electrolytic Solutions', London, Butterworths Scientific Publications (1959).

It may therefore, be inferred that under the conditions employed in the present investigation rhodamine B hydrochloride exists in nitrobenzene solution mainly in the associated form RH^+Cl^- . Ramette and Sandell⁹ have shown that the main cationic species in $5 \times 10^{-5} M$ rhodamine B solution in aqueous— HCl of pH 1–3 is RH^+ . Substoichiometric extraction of Re(VII) with nitrobenzene solution of RH^+Cl^- indicate (Fig. 1) that the extracted species contain RH^+ and ReO_4^- in the proportion of 1 : 1.

Fig. 1. Substoichiometric extraction of perrhenate by $7.671 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution of RH^+Cl^- in nitrobenzene from aqueous solution of pH 2.8. (equilibration time—2 minutes; volume of each phase = 20 ml).

The extraction of Re(VII) shows a first power dependence on the equilibrium concentration of RH^+Cl^- in nitrobenzene. The extraction equilibrium may, therefore be represented as

and

$$K = \frac{(\text{RH}^+\text{ReO}_4^-)_o(\text{Cl}^-)}{(\text{ReO}_4^-)(\text{RH}^+\text{Cl}^-)_o} = \frac{E(\text{Cl}^-)}{(\text{RH}^+\text{Cl}^-)_o} \quad (1a)$$

or

$$\log E + \log (\text{Cl}^-) = \log K + \log (\text{RH}^+\text{Cl}^-)_o \quad (1b)$$

where subscript 'o' signifies organic phase and other terms have their usual significance. When chloride ion concentration in the aqueous phase is constant, equation (1b) reduces to

$$\log E = \log K_1 + \log (\text{RH}^+\text{Cl}^-)_o, \quad \text{where } K_1 = \frac{K}{(\text{Cl}^-)}$$

In the present series of experiments, the concentration of chloride ion in the equilibrated aqueous phase at $pH\ 2.8$ has been maintained constant. Therefore, the plot of $\log E$ versus $\log (RH^+Cl^-)_0$ should be a straight line of unit slope, as observed (Fig. 2) experimentally. The average value of pK_1 is found to be 5.5 ± 0.1 .

Fig. 2. Extraction of perrhenate by nitrobenzene solution of RH^+Cl^- from aqueous solution at $pH\ 2.8$.

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